

Key takeaways from ENERGATE Greek Workshop

Discussion topics on energy-efficient building renovation in Greece

Current Challenges & Priorities

The energy-efficient building renovation sector in Greece faces several challenges and priorities that must be addressed to meet ambitious EU and national targets.

- Municipalities play a key role in energy-saving initiatives but are hindered by **bureaucratic obstacles and limitations within the energy sector**.

- Strengthening financial tools, establishing energy communities, enhancing production capacity, and fostering collaboration between municipalities, the state, and academia are **critical steps toward progress**.

- **Mobilising the mass renovation of energy-vulnerable households is also a priority**, emphasising the necessity of a well-organised energy-saving market, the implementation of deep building renovations to address energy poverty, and complementary set of tools, such as energy communities and Energy Performance Contracts.

Policy & Financial Needs

- **Innovative financing mechanisms** for mobilising the mass renovation of energy vulnerable households are essential to accelerate energy efficiency efforts in buildings.
- **National guidelines** should be further developed to align with EU goals while also considering Greece's socio-economic conditions.
- A significant **investment of €25 billion** is estimated to **upgrade buildings in category E or below by 2035**, with **another €25 billion allocated for phasing out boilers by 2040**.
- **Eliminating gaps in technical expertise and improving vocational education** are crucial for successfully implementing these initiatives.

ESCO Model & Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs)

The Energy Service Company (ESCO) model and Energy Performance Contracts (EPCs) are vital for financing large-scale retrofits. However, the lack of historical energy data prevents ESCOs from engaging in efficiency projects, as proven energy savings are required for funding. **EPCs offer a model where ESCOs invest in upgrades and recover costs through financial savings**, making them particularly useful for businesses and public buildings. Despite their benefits, **EPC contracts face barriers such as low familiarity, financing difficulties, and a shortage of skilled personnel**. These challenges can be mitigated by leveraging EU programmes, simplifying administrative processes, and promoting public-private cooperation.

Key Recommendations for Boosting the Market

- Improve financial availability and access to funding.
- Ensure availability of raw materials, equipment, and skilled workforce.
- Enhance stakeholder coordination.
- Train the workforce in new energy-saving technologies.
- Prioritise interventions: with building envelope improvements, followed by HVAC and renewable energy installations, and automation systems.
- Energy poverty and the critical role of government-backed networks and facilitators to coordinate public sector energy-saving initiatives,
- The importance of technical protocols for energy audits, where gaps hinder progress in regional areas like Macedonia and Thrace.
- Greek banks should mainly assess projects rather than solely focussing on financial background checks of their customers.

ENERGATE Platform – Key insights & recommendations

The **ENERGATE platform** was widely recognised as a transformative tool in the market, offering a **comprehensive, one-stop-shop solution for building renovations**. Its ability to **standardise processes such as data collection, project evaluation, and impact assessments across various building typologies** was highly valued by key industry stakeholders.

To enhance the platform's functionality and credibility, several recommendations were made:

- **Building Ownership Titles:** Ensure legal and ownership verification to secure investments.
- **Filtering Offers:** Allow users to sort financial tools based on their needs.
- **User Rewards:** Implement a rating system to incentivise active participation.
- **Offer Evaluation Algorithm:** Compare and rank investment offers.
- **Tailored Recommendations:** Improve transparency in energy-saving measure selection.
- **Flexible Proposal Packages:** Accommodate both large- and small-scale interventions, ensuring diverse energy-saving opportunities.
- **Incorporate diverse savings' indicators:** Track electricity, temperature, and humidity savings.
- **Digital Twin Technology:** Enable real-time energy monitoring for large buildings.
- **Financial Tools Integration:** Display available financing schemes, with a focus on residential projects.
- **ESCo Collaboration:** Secure long-term partnerships with ESCOs to sustain platform development beyond 2025.

Survey results on the current situation and the needs of the Greek market for energy efficiency projects and investments

The survey gathered responses from various stakeholders, with municipalities making up 50% of participants, alongside energy consultants, installers, and representatives from other European projects.

How are energy efficiency projects financed in Greece?

Energy efficiency projects in Greece are primarily financed through **European and national grants and subsidies**, with 75% of respondents confirming this as the most common funding method. Other financing options include **clients' own funds, regular loans, and green loans**, while mortgages, EPCs, and leasing are less common. On-bill financing remains rare due to its recent introduction. The limited use of EPCs highlights untapped potential for the EPC/ESCO model in Greece.

The most common financing options in Greece according to the respondents

The least common financing options in Greece according to the respondents

What are the most important barriers in the Greek market? How can the ENERGATE platform help to overcome them?

Key barriers to energy efficiency financing in Greece include complex procedures, a lack of suitable financing tools, and limited awareness among stakeholders. The ENERGATE platform has strong potential to address these challenges by **streamlining processes, standardising actions, increasing awareness of financing options, and improving communication among market actors.**

Barriers of energy efficiency financing in Greece

The potential of the ENERGATE platform and its services

Respondents recognised the platform's ability to centralise all relevant parties and project information, enabling direct connections and more efficient decision-making. The platform's services, such as **financial tool selection, financial metric calculations, project aggregation, matchmaking, and monitoring**, received high ratings (above 4/5). However, there was less interest in using it for EU taxonomy guidance.

With an overall rating of 4.13/5 and 87.5% of respondents expressing willingness to use it, the ENERGATE platform is seen as a valuable tool for advancing energy efficiency financing in Greece. The survey results provide crucial insights into market needs, helping ENERGATE refine its offerings and enhance its impact on the energy sector.

Rating the usefulness of ENERGATE services

energate-project.eu

[ENERGATEproject](https://www.youtube.com/ENERGATEproject)

[ENERGATE Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/ENERGATE-Project)

[Energate_eu](https://twitter.com/Energate_eu)

